

Abstract

On dreams. Discussion, hypotheses and case studies.

The phenomena of dreams

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1 Intro

Per my definitions of life[1], every life-form is a relative superposition of extroverted and introverted components.

Extroversion is manifested on the scale of physical interactions while introversion manifests on mental scales.

For dominantly extroverted creatures, dreams will generally be blurry (of low resolution) and may feel less real, lacking coherence. Dominantly introverted ones perceive reality in dreams or hallucinations, while their extroversion (external version of reality) is more blurry, feels less real (may be dominantly driven by the innate component of instinct and very predictable actions/reactions) and may lack coherence.

Nature of reality is thus relative to the class of a life-form (dominance of extroversion vs introversion). However, extroverted and introverted realities are correlated.

Questioning the meaning of dreams can thus be relatively equivalent to questioning the meaning of life or reality. Here, I will try to shed some light on the nature and function of dreams, in the process also analysing some peculiar dreams of my own. Certain hypotheses will also be presented here, however, most evidence for these may be found in my other works.

2 What are dreams?

A dream is a type of hallucination - one in which subconsciousness dominates over conscious operation for extroverted creatures (thus, for introverted creatures, "dream" may be an inappropriate term, as for such creatures this hallucination is consciously experienced and can be as real as the experience of external reality by extroverts).

Note that, even though the introverted component is not insignificant in humans (in some more than in others), all contemporary humans are still dominantly extroverted creatures, including the, so called, "introverts". Thus, in this context, all humans are extroverts, and the term "introvert" has a different meaning - it represents a lifeform whose reality is dominantly internally generated - which is not the case for conventional introverts (although conventional introversion may be a precursor to more pronounced real introversion).

We hallucinate all the time (at least per my definition of hallucination[2]), however, when we're not dreaming, our subconsciousness is generally subdued and conscious experience dominates our reality.

The reality human beings perceive in daily operation is reality first experienced by physical organs, relayed to our brains, then interpreted by the brain and finally consciously experienced by the soul (which makes it clear that even the experience of this reality is a hallucination - it is interpretation dependent). However, as the brains are generally layered, consciousness is generally layered too. Deeper layers of consciousness (subconsciousness) may not be so active in mental expression (such expression is subdued) during daily operation but they are still active, e.g. in data collection, organization and storage.

Of course, some information is processed consciously during daily operation, but this conscious processing is spatio-temporally limited, with limits being proportional to the amount of extroversion in the perception of reality. Subconsciousness, however, is much less localized, enabling a more holistic information processing, that in humans occurs mainly during REM sleep.

There are two main types of sleep, NREM and REM (short for 'Rapid-Eye-Movement') sleep. During NREM sleep memories (experiences) are consolidated, relayed from short-term storage to long-term storage. During REM sleep, collected information is processed, but in a different way than during wakefulness, generally exhibiting a more holistic and higher (less biased) intelligence than during wakefulness.

For additional information on dreams and phases of sleep, I highly recommend the excellent book "Why We Sleep: Unlocking the Power of Sleep and Dreams", by M. Walker[3].

To dream, then, is to change context, or a reference frame - in a dream, consciousness and subconsciousness effectively exchange places. Consciousness is diluted or subdued, while subconsciousness is the guiding force.

The lack of consciousness is the reason why we usually don't remember much of our dreams. But this, of course, depends on the amount of extroversion. Those who experience lucid dreaming have at least some amount of conscious control. Thus, lucid dreaming is probably a sign of developing higher introversion in the experience of reality, and may be a precursor of dominance of introversion.

Obviously, dreams are far from being meaningless. Regardless of the content of the dream, while we are dreaming, our mentality and our epigenome is changing in the background, making each one of us a slightly different person in the morning.

However, what here represents the background operation can be relative, in cases where the dream is controlled, the dream itself may have significant influence on physiological changes, in other cases - where the control is lacking, it may simply be the equivalent of a desktop screensaver (common software in older computers whose main purpose is to prevent *fossilization* of images on computer screens, and perhaps provide some limited entertainment to the idling user in case that user is not absent) that may or may not be much correlated with ongoing changes.

But how localized is the subconsciousness, active during sleep? While this probably depends on species, subspecies[4] and the individual, can there be precognition?

Even the less localized consciousness has predictive power, so the predictive power of subconsciousness should be greater. But can it be powerful enough to become effective precognition?

This is probably possible - with sufficient information, sufficient quality of information, and sufficient subconscious intelligence (lack of bias). Obviously, not everyone will dream *future*. A creature that is mostly concerned with short-term interests during wakefulness is probably unlikely to process information highly correlated with deep past or deep future even in dreams. Even if such information is processed, it is likely to be marginalized or misinterpreted.

The key to precognition is knowledge of the past and present, and the less localized is that information the better. While absolute precognition is impossible due to inherent limitations on observability (information sharing), a solid approximation of future will probably occasionally play out in the dreams of some individuals.

It should be noted that, while dreams may contain past experiences, these are typically not in the original form, rather a contemporary interpretation - augmented or superposed with correlated more recent experiences. And this is probably true for any possible *echoes* of future in dreams as well. Thus, proper interpretation of potential future will

probably require proper extrapolation.

Precognition thus requires information sharing/collection, and the more dimensions (levels) this includes, the more accurate the precognition can potentially be.

Animals like people are consciously communicating and sharing information between each other. Now, since universes (layers of consciousness - in this context) are self-similar, some subconscious [horizontal] information collection and sharing between individuals is likely to exist as well. Information transfer is thus layered too, both vertically (between brain layers of the individual) and horizontally (between equivalent layers in different individuals). Layers within layers are likely to exist too (self-similarity) and, theoretically, the range of subconsciousness may be unlimited, although individually it must be limited.

This is based on the theory of Complete Relativity[5] (CR) (see chapter *Strong entanglement*), where I have equalized souls with graviton particles.

Deeper levels are less localized in space/time (in quantum interpretation - field carrier particle has lower energy and thus longer range).

Note that, at some scale (level), this becomes inter-species communication - a lot of DNA is shared between species and certain equivalence between brain layers exists. It is possible, however, that a layer of subconsciousness in one species corresponds to a layer of consciousness in the other. In any case, all the communicated information, properly processed, can provide a solid basis for precognition.

The communication, however, doesn't necessarily involve only DNA-carrying forms of energy, or, what is the conventional interpretation of a lifeform (as it is conventionally biased).

Note also that the type of information processing is not scale invariant. In case of higher localization, for example, processing is dominantly deterministic, on less-localized levels it becomes more quantum-like.

Some studies have been done on precognition in dreams[6], however, there hasn't been much research into the phenomena overall, and no study has ever discriminated between subspecies[4] (polarized, neutral) of humans.

2.1 Dreams in synchronicity, synchronicity in dreams

Entanglement (correlation) often involves resonance or synchronization, which conventionally requires force. A special case of entanglement is synchronicity - a consciously sensible but apparently non-forced synchronization of correlated phenomena. Forced synchronization generally involves high localization of energy. Non-forced one does not.

Thus, people experiencing synchronicity are those more *in tune* with the environment - through less-localized (subconscious) entanglements. While the experience of synchronicity is prone to conscious misinterpretation, regular experience of synchronicity probably indicates higher range and deeper role of subconsciousness in the physiology and experience of reality of the individual. In other words, consciously recognized synchronicity may be a symptom of highly active, potent or highly evolving subconscious - which should be reflected in sleep and dreams.

Indeed, my sleeping and dreaming has, for example, significantly changed with the strong physiological transformation experienced about the age of 36-37. My dreams are now far more interesting, more coherent and meaningful, sometimes lucid, and sometimes they reach far into the past, sometimes into the future.

At least that's how I feel about such dreams. Of course, I cannot be sure that what seems to me like future actually is a highly probable future - those who claim extreme certainty in predictions of future are usually delusional. I can do a deeper research on past and contemporary events to assess the likelihood for the dreamed event to play out in the future, but ultimately, time will tell. If time, however, confirms such prediction, the hypothesis probably should be taken seriously.

But this change was coupled with the experience of synchronicity. I didn't experience synchronicity before this transformation, now I experience it regularly.

During the transformation, however, I was regularly overwhelmed with synchronicity. So much so that the external reality I experienced looked like someone's dream.

3 The power of hallucinations

During our early development (mostly embryonic), our physical activity is very limited and low and our consciousness is not well localized, our subconsciousness may be more localized (at some level - level probably changing with development) but our dreams or hallucinations at that time are experienced in very low resolution (as our brains are not much developed).

In my theories, the delocalized consciousness during development is extremely important as it is the phenomenon guiding organismal development (the DNA genome contains recipes for the manufacture of components but doesn't drive overall development). The soul (carrier of consciousness) contains the relative equivalent of a genome. However this genome does not contain recipes, rather hallucinations that extend temporally, and significantly into future. The soul is thus guiding living components of the body so their shared reality converges to a particular outcome (a goal in the quantum of development, or, quantum of local evolution). The guidance is achieved through attractors or imprints (hallucinations, or relative equivalents of dark matter filaments or curvature, but of smaller scale) in mental space-time (which is a smaller scale of space-time, ruled by different, more complex, forces).

Note that this implies that organs, cells, and even smaller components, are distinct living beings - sensitive to curvature in mental space to a certain degree even though they may not possess brain equivalents. Some might argue that the hypothesis presented here is unnecessary to explain what we observe and, hence, unscientific. That's a common argument of excessive reductionists, however, it is flawed for the following reasons:

- it's based on a very narrow perspective - I have shown through my works that the existence of some kind of souls and associated fields is necessary to explain multiple observed phenomena (some seemingly unrelated) on various scales,
- this existence is actually not unnecessary even in this limited context, as it will be argued below,
- the argument is not even a proper argument, rather an assumption emerging from the abuse of the Occam's razor,
- a lot of organization in organismal development is unexplained, and there are still a lot of unknowns in the function of the brain, it has not been proved - and probably never will be - that consciousness is an emergent phenomenon not requiring anything more than the sum of computational units in a neural network (quite contrary, one could argue that contemporary computer science and technology have actually already proved that assumption to be false).

There are many things we cannot access directly, yet we are certain of their existence. That is the case for mentality as well. For example, the image of the world that exists in a dream must physically exist somewhere, but even though one can influence this image through brain control one cannot access it directly. In other words, we may have access to the computer but not to the screen. The screen thus exists on a scale

(dimension) inaccessible to us but it certainly exists, even if we cannot measure it directly (all observers of reality are inherently limited, albeit not equally). I refer to this scale of space-time as mental space-time (this is where not only dreams, but thoughts, experiences and feelings in general play out). On that scale reality is more quantum-like, and this quantum-like mentality is probably the underlying reason why gene regulatory networks exhibit quantum-like behaviour[7] and why REM sleep intelligence is quantum-like (the approach to problem solving is more holistic and the emergence of the solution looks like a result of collapse of superposed correlations[8]). We already know that mentality can influence physicality and *vice versa*. What I propose is physical duality of the two, where the two exist on different scales but are entangled and mutual causal relationship is relative. Sometime the mind (soul) will affect the body, sometimes *vice versa* - implying that they do not evolve independently - when coupled, at least.

Note that mental guidance, being directly unmeasurable, can be interpreted as free will of the guided, but it's obviously only relatively free. Note also that both, proponents of conventional duality (where soul is assumed to be unphysical) and reductionists, actually believe in magic. The former are *a priori* rejecting possibility of scientific explanation, while the latter believe that mental experiences (such as thoughts, feelings, or consciousness in general) magically appear at certain level of physical complexity. To reductionists, the activity of the brain, for example, somehow is a direct representation of the image in the mind, an absurd notion by which our computers should have started dreaming long ago and we would know it - not only that, but what they propose is equivalent to saying that we do not need computer screens and printers because the activity of central processing units (CPU's) and graphics processing units (GPU's) represent the image. Well, I don't know about the population of excessive reductionists, but no matter how hard I look at my graphics card I just cannot see a realistic interpretation of Mr. Edward running with scissors. In fact, all I can see is the graphics card itself. Sure, I could put electrodes on the graphics card and try to create an image from the output, but I'm not reading the image itself, I'm reading data that requires specific transformation to be interpreted as image. In other words, I need some kind of a screen. Thus, with no mind-body duality, the image that we see in our minds would have to exist in our brains in exactly the same form. If it doesn't exist there in exactly the same form (and apparently it doesn't) then it isn't there. All considered, from a non-biased or holistic perspective, it should be clear that:

- brain is a computational unit, but it is not the *screen* (in this context, "screen" should be translated as a real multidimensional world on some scale of reality),

- a hormone excretion may correlate with feelings, but it is not a feeling itself,
- etc.

And this is one reason why dreams, or hallucinations in general, are important, or, have great power - because diluted consciousness (active subconsciousness) can guide the components of our body towards a particular outcome. As the correlation between the current state of development and the end state grows, the associated soul is increasingly being localized. As the adult stage is reached, the localization stops, there is no more active development/growth, only transformation and maintenance.

A phase shift can exist between the soul and the organized tissue. The soul may be changing [discrete] horizontal energy levels (representing effective goals of development) relatively instantly, while the body evolves continuously. Once the body reaches a particular eigenstate, the soul jumps to a higher level, driving development (evolution) further. Jumps to lower horizontal energy levels should be correlated with ageing reversals, while changes in the vertical energy level should be correlated with body decay and decoupling of souls and bodies.

But guidance is not impossible in the adult stage and can be correlated with evolution or maintenance of energy levels. For example, diseases can be a threat to the stability of body-soul coupling on a particular energy level. Subconscious guidance can be useful in such cases.

G-Tummo meditation is an obvious example of internal guidance in adults, where meditators can induce physical thermogenesis by neurocognitive visualization[9]. In other words, they can elevate their body temperature simply by imagining the body on fire. But there are also cases where people have been effectively curing diseases mentally (I believe I am one of them). Obviously, souls are very powerful so it's not surprising people generally don't have full control over them. In other words, people usually control consciousness, but not the subconscious - which can influence the body through mental pathways. Some people (usually deep meditators), however, obviously can effectively do this consciously - which can be interpreted as a stronger form of lucid dreaming. But what exactly happens here? Does the consciousness itself transition into the subconscious realm without losing control of reality, or does it somehow gain control of the subconscious? In any case, the apparent control may be effective, not real. Mental world is a quantum world and strong causality may not be involved - effective conscious guidance present here can be a manifestation of synchronicity, when the entanglement between consciousness and subconsciousness is elevated. In that case,

the apparent "free will" leading to hallucination may itself be a manifestation of entanglement, without involving causal information exchange through consciousness delocalization (information exchange doesn't happen during active entanglement - information is transferred during changes in entanglement, and that occurs with localization/delocalization of consciousness). In synchronicity there is no apparent information transfer and conscious guidance is in that case an illusion which may be interpreted as an effect of high synchronization of consciousness and subconsciousness. In other words, the desired future state of the individual is equal to the most likely future state of that individual, with no apparent causality relationship between the two. Information buffering, for eventual transfer, however, cannot be excluded, and one may ask, how exactly the two got synchronized (entangled) and maintained synchronization if not by information exchanges? Thus, the entanglement/synchronization is probably a consequence of periodic information exchanges, even though there may be no information exchange during the synchronicity event itself.

In any case, if one can effectively induce changes in the body through imagination without deep meditation (e.g., cause the symptoms of allergy to disappear) and the effect is apparent with no changes in the state of consciousness in between, it's probably safe to assume this is a manifestation of high synchronization, low causation.

Correlation between subconsciousness and consciousness differs between species, subspecies and individuals of these subspecies. For some it could be normal to imagine effects or guidance correlated with what's happening inside their bodies, for some the probability for this could be high some time (e.g., during deep meditation), for some it could almost never happen. The information exchange leading to high entanglement between consciousness and the subconscious can be interpreted as symbiosis between consciousness and subconsciousness. Most people, however, belong to subspecies that has learned to ignore or negatively interact with the subconscious, rather than cooperate (the increasing consumption of pills, for example, in order to numb the symptoms of diseases, is one example of silencing of subconscious messengers, thus highly correlated with decreasing symbiosis).

This is then not easily reproducible in studies with usual cohorts, as it may be impossible for the dominant subspecies of humans to reproduce this [effective] power, that some clearly do have. To obtain it, one would need to evolve in a certain direction. Likely towards decreased extroverted polarization and increased symbiotic introversion.

Self-similarity of universes is correlated with oscillation of souls through vertical energy levels. This is why dark matter filaments (guiding stan-

dard matter) between galaxies are relatively equivalent to the effects (goals) in guidance during embryonic organismal development. It is also the reason behind similarity of planetary systems and atoms (which becomes striking when subatomic particles are localized[10]).

The code may be universal, the difference is in interpretation - e.g., what is interpreted as space on one scale, on other it may be interpreted as time. Regarding evolution, the nature doesn't seem to generally have a preferred path, as long as all paths lead to the same goal in roughly the same time.

4 The impact of the stress barrier

Ignoring outcomes of subconscious processing will probably influence dreams in a locally negative way and will lead to subduction of subconscious long-range influence potential in the long-term.

Increasing ignorance of subconsciousness leads to loss, or outsourcing, of control or power (e.g., outsourcing of the immune system), where the individual is losing ability for improvisation or deviation from the guidance of *collective* hallucination. In other words, its action is converging towards being nothing more than a positive feedback, accelerating transition to the next evolutionary eigenstate of the society (e.g., subspecies collective) it is a part of.

But the subduction of subconscious certainly doesn't lead to increasing amount of consciousness. In the process, consciousness is probably reducing to awareness (similar to its state during embryonic development) and the being is concentrating on shorter and shorter short-term interests, eventually becoming nothing more than a deterministic machine reacting to external stimuli from an external perspective (similar to the conventional interpretation of living animal cells, although these still may have more complex introversion).

Stress may be the source of many diseases, but it is also a strong barrier preventing one to get in touch with its spirituality, correlated with deeper layers of consciousness.

Daily life of extroverted human society is life in constant anticipation of a next stressful event. Everything is externally programmed and people are consciously and unconsciously trained to react to external stimuli and perform externally programmed routines, all on a promise of some material award.

Most people are addicted to these routines, and with neglected spiritual aspects of being, they are in a controlled state of heavy imbalance (polarization).

A good quality rest and sleep is of great importance for spirituality, internal communication within the body, its immune system, but also mental communication.

If such meaningful sleep is reduced to a pause between stressful events, there

will be consequences.

The imbalance is extremely unhealthy if one is to conserve the amount of distinct consciousness over generations - if one subdues subconsciousness, the consciousness will follow, reducing the amount of space/time one is aware of during any operation.

People don't even notice most of the stress their organism is exposed to and situations which it might not enjoy - they have been trained not to care about it.

On one occasion, while I was grinding some metal pipe, a tiny fragment of metal flew into my eye and glued to the eyeball.

I was told that the only way to solve the problem is to go see a physician, otherwise this could lead to extreme complications and I might even go blind. It's not just common people, this is what physicians are saying too. But I know that physicians are trained to believe in such things - one's disease is their job, and it just seemed to me extremely unlikely that this cannot be solved by my organism.

I tried to fix it myself but it didn't work, so I just decided not to force anything and continued with the *experiment*.

Over the next couple of days it was very painful to use both eyes. Changes in brightness were particularly painful. This is when I noticed how much strain is experienced by eyes and that watching television is, with constant changes in brightness and sound, generally extremely stressful for the organism.

Most stressful here are short clips, such as advertisements, where there is a tendency to present as much information as possible in smallest amount of time possible.

These things are not only generally insulting in multiple ways, they are shocking.

Although painful, synchronization of pain with changes in visual stimuli was interesting, especially watching fireworks - with every explosion observed I would feel a surge of pain in the eye.

For some time I was also experiencing an interesting side-effect to this eye state, something I could notice only while watching stars.

Usually, I would see a star as a single bright spot with a short vertical line through it. Sometimes I would also observe reddish and bluish dots at endpoints of the line.

But in this condition, with injured eye open, I would also see a horizontal [slightly curved] line at the bottom, so stars looked to me like upside-down crosses of Christ.

After a week or two the pain subdued and after a month the metal fragment was gone from my eye and it was completely cured.

I have learned a lot from this experiment. Instead of trusting a physician and letting my self be ruled by fear I chose to trust my body and I was

not disappointed.

Sure, there was pain, but there was more gain. One loses trust, confidence and the ability of self-regulation while *outsourcing* regulation - and that's something I am not comfortable with.

That does not mean everyone should be forced to trust the ecosystem of their bodies - polarized people, in general, may be comfortable with outsourced regulation (which is probably correlated with the fact that they can't trust their bodies due to subdued subconsciousness).

5 Precognition

With relative causality, dreaming events that have a high probability of occurring in future should not be impossible. Here, the accuracy and probability should depend on species/sub-species and the individual, however, I am not aware of any such significant, credible, confirmed predictions, far into future.

On the other hand, short-term accurate predictions might be common, at least in some individuals.

To me, it occasionally happens that, while dreaming, the brain incorporates external information into the dream, apparently real-time. In example, a louder noise of a passing vehicle results in the rendering of a passing vehicle making the sound in the dream. Generally, waking up follows shortly after.

And perhaps this would not be surprising if the effect would affect the context of the dream, however, incorporation of the effect in the dream is seamless and perfectly natural (not something that appears suddenly out of nowhere, unexpectedly, out of context).

It is hard to attribute this synchronicity to coincidence, the effect suggests that *the brain* anticipated the specific external stimulation - in this case, passing of a vehicle.

The anticipation might not be surprising if such stimulation is common (as it would be, in this case, if one would be sleeping next to a highway) but it generally isn't so (and even if it is, probability for such precise synchronization would still be lower than what is experienced).

I am not the only one who has been experiencing this phenomenon - a colleague of mine has been experiencing it too. Thus, it is probably not uncommon, at least in some type (subspecies) of human individuals.

It should be noted, however, that in some cases, what seems like external simulation of senses might be an internally generated hallucination itself.

Obviously, it makes sense that during sleep *the brain* (more precisely, our

soul, consciousness or subconsciousness) is not fully oblivious to external activity. In example, translating a potentially life-threatening external phenomenon into a traumatic experience inside the dream could make the person wake up and able to react to immediate danger outside.

It is even more beneficial that the experience in the dream is not only synchronized with, rather precedes, the external stimulation. The postulated relativity of causality in CR allows this. But is this limited to short-term predictions?

Theoretically, of course, not. In reality, it makes sense that those with inherent long-term interests should be more likely to dream farther into future.

UPDATE 2023.10.06

I had another similar dream. While I was sleeping a kid was playing with a soccer ball outside. In the dream there was a woman sitting behind the desk. At one point she slams the desk hard with her hand and at exactly the same point in time the ball hit the house door, so hard that it woke me up (well, I guess it's debatable what actually caused my awakening but generally people would blame the ball, or the kid). This is another evidence that synchronicity and subconsciousness (introversion) are strongly correlated. Again, it seems like my subconsciousness knew well in advance that the ball is going to hit the door (the dream was, again, seamless). This could also be interpreted as evidence that events constantly occur simultaneously on various scales - only the interpretation is different. This was obviously not a result of experience on the scale we usually refer to as physical. I don't think we can physically sense with great precision what's going on outside, behind the concrete walls, especially during sleep. I guess my ear (yes, one ear, I was sleeping on the other) could have picked up the sound of the ball at some point but I don't think there was a way to figure out from that information that it's going to hit the door. And, even if there was, it couldn't be so seamlessly incorporated into the dream - there simply was no time for that.

Therefore, there are two possible interpretations (which are not mutually exclusive) - subconscious precognition and temporal synchronicity (entanglement in time).

6 Hallucinating transition

Effectively, hallucination is a superposition of external reality and local projection. It should be a common phenomenon in species transitioning from dominantly extroverted consciousness to introverted consciousness, which should be

a part of progressive evolution.

As numerous experiences show, life in dreams can be as complex, coherent and real as it is in external reality. Besides internal hallucinations, another indication of transition is, thus, increasing complexity and consistency of dreams.

This has been evident in my dreams - some of my dreams had consistent, complex and intelligent stories which could be translated into fine movies. Sometimes, I have even worked on my theories in dreams.

The transition is also correlated with increasing interaction with non-conscious entities (machines) and decreasing ability to express greater consciousness and intelligence within the society without the aid of intermediate non-conscious information carriers. Increasing depression and anxiety in external reality should then not be surprising with such development.

However, transition is unlikely to be linear - elsewhere, I have hypothesized oscillating oscillation between extroversion and introversion of life during evolution, thus, even though extroversion may be declining, the transition itself should oscillate.

In my case, I have felt significant anxiety and depression during early life and now these feelings are gone. However, my interactions in external reality have significantly decreased and I often find myself avoiding complex interactions and expression in external reality.

Not all individuals of species share the same evolutionary path though, divergence is expectable - some may continue progressive evolution, some might regress, even if temporarily.

Also, some will likely oscillate about a *comfortable mean* (otherwise life on Earth would lack diversity and probably couldn't exist at all).

7 Cryptic dreams

If temporal localization of consciousness is particularly low (as it may be occasionally in some individuals), effectively, dreams may not be correlated with the current incarnation of the body, rather past or future one. This may not be real personal future or past of the soul of the individual, only the difference (or uncertainty) may be so low that it can be interpreted as personal.

Entanglement (more precisely, its oscillation) is the key for information collection by the subconscious, and this is the information dreams are based on (information is transmitted during changes in entanglement between entangled entities). While this information may usually be locally collected, resulting in dreams based on local experience (information collected in near space/time and collected directly by the local subconscious), this may not always be the case.

Note that the brain and consciousness (including deeper layers or the subconscious) are entangled but they are not one and the same. Information transfer, being based on entanglement, thus does not have to be

local.

As noted before, this will depend on species, subspecies and individuals. Even though the subconscious of the dominant subspecies of humans is generally short-sighted (in space/time), I believe this is not the case with the neutral subspecies. At least some of the neutral individuals will effectively possess a *6th sense*, collecting information at greater distances (in space/time) and thus not necessarily experienced by the local individual. The boundaries of beings are relative and these boundaries are even more plastic for consciousness and its deeper layers (subconscious). Two highly correlated entities (e.g., twins) may often exhibit quantum-like entanglement on some level. Similar to the gravitational fields, consciousness is best described by the fields of potential. A visible body or a brain can be interpreted as a highly localized high-energy manifestation of the associated field potential maximum. It is correlated with deeper layers of the individual but, with decreasing energy, these deeper layers have a proportionally longer range (an individual is a superposition of fields of potential of different carrier energies and polarization). In any of these fields, information transfer occurs whenever/wherever there is a change in energy (entanglement), but since all these fields are mutually entangled as well, information transfer does not occur only horizontally, but vertically as well (e.g., from deeper subconscious to consciousness). All "individuals" are bathing in this sea of information, but the amount, quality and type (range) of information collected, analysed and interpreted locally will depend on the individual.

A body can be interpreted as an localized excitation of fields of potentials. But this excitation is a result of vertical information transfer (between different scales/species of potential), which is correlated with horizontal information transfer. On the level of the individual, this transfer is highest and least localized at conception (note that molecular *twins* exist all across the observable universe), it remains high during embryonic development (note that relatively the same tissues of cells/proteins are shared between different species, particularly during early embryonic development), while in the adult stage it reaches its minimum (most complex forms are most rare, note also that the speed of information transfer is inversely proportional to scale). This is why development of organ(ism)s is so robust and predictable (positive feedbacks between entangled entities exist - a *snapshot* of a more advanced remote development becomes a relative goal locally, guiding local development, more precisely, local development is guided towards the superposition of goals where stronger entanglements have stronger influence, note that this implies that for every *egg* these must exist a *chicken* somewhere, no matter how remote in space/time) but it also implies that a change in the development of

one species can affect other species, more the more entangled the species are. In the adult stage, on the individual level, we're not as sensitive to changes in species, rather more to changes in subspecies and individuals. This is because, effectively, both vertical and horizontal range of information transfer is reduced. However, as noted previously, these limitations are relative, will differ between individuals and can even change dramatically during the adult stage (correlated with transformation of consciousness).

Dreams, hallucinations or visions can thus be more local or more remote (in space/time), generally, a relative superposition of both. The individual should be able to *feel* the difference between the phenomena based on local information (experience) and remote information (experience), because the local experience should also be highly correlated with the local body (e.g., brain).

Indeed, lately I am experiencing more and more of the phenomena I strongly feel are based on remote information. Some of these extraordinary events (which are apparently becoming ordinary) will be presented here. Some of these qualify as potential experiences of different incarnations of my soul, while some (if not all) may represent experiences of other souls mine is currently correlated with, or was highly correlated at the time of information collection (usually probably within the day before the dream).

While I might refer to them as personal, considering the fact that souls evolve and that a soul (and indirectly, brain) might even be interpreting data from a brain-soul coupling on another Earth-like planet (or *anti-brain* on *anti-Earth*) it is entangled with (entanglement can exist across vast distances), this personality can be very relative.

However, the source signals are probably not, nor do they have to be, as remote (check *Memory of soul's past lives* chapter in *Solution to gravitational anomalies*[11]). In any case, local information should usually have priority.

Assuming the souls are more or less complex quantum particles, the sex/gender is likely correlated with spin/chirality of the soul, so if a soul is male on one planet, in case of anti-aligned spin entanglement, it will be female on the other.

The sex is generally well preserved over incarnations on the same scale because the collapse (death or soul-body decoupling) generally requires spin change of the soul. Since soul inflation (coupling) also requires a change of spin, it has to be equal to the one in the previous incarnation. Exceptions to this rule are possible, e.g., in cases where as some point in the adulthood, the soul reaches a higher energy level than in the previous incarnation (in other words, it *permanently* evolves). Since this

jump also requires spin change, decoupling (assuming it is not gradual) will result in a different spin than the one in previous decoupling. Sex of the soul associated with the brain is correlated with the sex of the soul associated with reproductive organs. But different alignments here are possible, reflecting as hetero-, homo-, or bi-sexuality.

7.1 Incognita

A very unusual dream. Prior to this one, I never had a dream where I had a female body, but this time I had a strong feeling I was in the body of a woman.

She was pushed and fell into a shallow pool of water. Water was immediately filled with blood, so she was probably stabbed. I woke up afterwards. The phrase "*Ordi nami*" was ringing in my head (chanting). Everything suggests this was some kind of a sacrifice ritual.

I had a strong feeling this was a middle aged woman (30-40 years old) even though I do not remember the body (only roughly). This dream had, what I consider, a typical signature of a retro-vision. Most convincing evidence is that phrase which I have never heard in this life.

After I did some research, I realized the word *ordinami* exists in Italian language, meaning *order me* in English. Based on this and the theorized inclination of my soul orbital[12], the location should probably be somewhere in the Eastern Roman empire (possibly eastern Greece, or closer to Egypt - Jerusalem?) during the medieval period. A more recent date probably cannot be ruled out, but such rituals in recent times don't seem likely.

Of course, some possibility exists I did hear this phrase somewhere but I just don't remember it. The odds for this are, however, low. I don't even remember when was the last time I heard someone speaking Italian. There are no Italian-speaking people anywhere nearby. Probably the only possible way I could have heard this phrase would be some movie I watched sometime in the past. However, I never watch Italian-speaking movies. And even if I did hear it before, why would my brain or soul construct this entire scene about the phrase, and why now? Sure, perhaps I have subconsciously memorized the entire scene from some movie long ago and this is it, but I am not convinced. After all, I wasn't watching the scene here, I was in it!

If this is indeed a memory of one of *my* previous deaths it would be interesting to know who that was.

However, in case of correlation with past incarnations or anti-incarnations, since my soul is male, the woman probably had to be either:

- homosexual, and/or accused of homosexuality - which could be the reason of sacrifice,
- living on *anti-Earth* (probably unlikely).

Evidence suggests that oscillation of male souls (associated with gender) between male and female bodies (associated with sex), and vice versa[13], is not unusual. If the oscillation is interpreted as karmic, such cycling becomes expectable.

7.1.1 The clues in timing

Note that I had this dream not long after the strong soul-body transformation event about the age of 36 (in fact, I never had such extraordinary dreams before this transformation). This is the transformation that made me neutral (even effectively asexual, one reason being the lack of neutral females about).

Even though I still feel sexual attraction to polarized females, the instinct/urge for relationships has been subdued so much that I have been comfortably alone for years now.

In one interpretation, this is because a female soul coupled to my male soul/body with the transformation event. Therefore, this dream may be based on the information (experiences) that came with that soul.

7.1.2 Evilization (2025.02.11)

While a retro-vision is not necessarily based on the past experience of the soul experiencing the retro-vision itself, strong correlation between the two souls is implied. It is thus more likely than not for it to be based on a *personal* past experience.

Taking this into consideration, and elsewhere hypothesized preservation of certain soul characteristics over incarnations, I believe I have now identified a good candidate for this woman - Hypatia, a female philosopher from Alexandria. According to historical sources, she was attacked and dragged from the street by an angry mob of Christians into a former pagan temple, a centre of the Roman imperial cult, converted into a Christian church. There she was murdered in such a frenzy of atrocity[14] that the devil himself would be left scratching his head pondering what on Earth possessed them. This murder marked the beginning of the Dark Ages. Obviously, Italian language was not spoken in the Alexandria in the 5th century, but Latin definitely was. A phrase "Ordina mihi" exists in Latin, which sounds the same when spoken and has the same meaning as Italian "ordinami". Note that it is widely believed that Hypatia's murder was ordered. Why did the mob drag her into the church? I can imagine some authority was waiting inside. It is quite possible that they were asking this

authority to order them to kill her by chanting "Ordina mihi". Latin language was used by the officials there.

I still question whether I should take the chanting I've heard in the dream literally, or as symbolic (subconscious suggestion that the murder was ordered and that it is somehow correlated with Latin language). Probably both. The latter would suggest that my subconscious has at least some understanding of the Latin language. This further suggests that substantial amount of knowledge/memory may be preserved between incarnations - not limited to experiences of traumatic events. This seems like good news - it could explain the Savant syndrome and makes one wonder whether this information could become accessible in a controlled way.

Hypatia was probably about 43 years old at the time of death (or, possibly about 37). Note that Hypatia was a lifelong virgin, one reason for this may be that she had a male soul, even though the body was a female one. Thus, it is possible that the mob had seen her as homosexual, even if that wasn't the primary reason of their anger. In fact, I believe there is a good probability that this woman was one of the incarnations of the same soul that was occupying the body of Jesus. In any case, one could interpret the brutal murder of this woman as a killing of Jesus, even if not literally. It makes one wonder, how many times have the Christian zealots killed the Jesus, simply because that "Jesus" is something much different than what they want *him* to be? Such a perverse cult Christianity is, and yet many to this day proudly associate themselves with the institution.

Cyril, the man responsible for the murder of Hypatia (and a bunch of other atrocities) has even been declared a saint, commemorated to this day by the Catholic church (and related churches)! I do not know what would be more ironic..

Once again, we live in times of a falling empire, once again, dark ages seem to lie ahead.. One can only hope all these perverse cults will dissolve into oblivion before they, once again, produce these savage zealots to proudly manifest the evil hiding behind the, so called, advanced civilization. Sure, zealots are always present, but it is the dark ages in which they thrive. Like a beast that only comes out at night, these are the times when they can, without fear, show what they really are.

7.2 Ghost car

I had a dream where I was in, what felt like, rural England, perhaps 18-19th century.

I felt I was driving some kind of a vehicle, sitting front right.

I felt one or two people were sitting behind me. However, no parts of the vehicle were rendered, it just felt like a vehicle and it was moving forward.

Soon I've seen a kid or two ahead. At that moment I felt someone from behind put something like a bag on my head at which point it all went blank and I woke up.

The fact that the vehicle was not rendered (likely it was so different from a car, a vehicle which I am experienced in driving this incarnation, that the brain couldn't associate it with that vehicle and render as such) suggests the information comes from a different age.

This may then be a retro-vision. The fact that I was sitting on the right while driving also goes in favour of that hypothesis, because I only drove cars with a steering wheel on the left in the current incarnation.

I am not sure if this was a moment of death, but it certainly was some traumatic experience - another signal favouring retro-vision.

7.3 Living in a game

I recently had an extraordinary dream.

It featured some weird creatures I have never seen in real life, including two human-like chimeras looking like devils.

What was fascinating to me were details in rendering. I have never had a dream previously where I could see such fine details on creatures or environment.

There were some complex interactions and it was like I was in some sort of a computer game, only it was as detailed and real as real life.

Note that I rarely play video games and when I do they are usually old 2D games.

Also note that a human brain has extreme processing capabilities, it is not only a supercomputer compared to ordinary computers, but it is a supercomputer to supercomputers built by man.

Obviously, its plasticity is also extreme, which is why it can produce high-quality simulations at *will*, something it might not usually be doing. High resolution of experience in dreams could be interpreted as a signal of transition towards a greater dominance of introversion.

The only reason I figured [in the dream itself] I am in a dream was because I have never seen these creatures in external reality (even though these dreams feel real, I am still dominantly an extroverted life-form, and this connection

with external reality will sometimes produce a feeling of non-belonging to a particular dream).

Due to complex coherent rendering and high resolution, I believe this dream was either scripted and generated *in situ* or it is strongly correlated with a near (in space and/or time) virtual reality (VR) experience. But what are the odds for spontaneous local generation of such content, especially for one without VR experience?

Often, when I go to sleep while my mind is in overdrive, at some point the line between a dream and dominant reality becomes very blurry. I am convinced I did some work in my dreams while working on CR.

7.4 Death of Tesla?

Tesla probably did not speak publicly about reincarnation as it was against the religious beliefs of his family, his father especially. But he probably believed in reincarnation (which was present in early Christianity), even if not conventional interpretations thereof.

Once I had a vision of, what I believe was, his death - where it appears he tried to force his soul to enter a particular body at that moment.

I saw a young couple. First, the man entered the hotel room, while the woman was waiting outside. After some short interaction, I was lying on bed. I've heard the man mentioning a vacuum cleaner (in Croatian or Serbian language) and the woman entered the room.

The woman came close to me, put my head on her abdomen. I died shortly after.

Why the woman/abdomen? It was probably assumed here she was in a state primed for the coupling of a soul to an egg. And minimized distance between the soul and the potential new body was probably assumed to increase the probability for coupling.

Why did I feel like I was N. Tesla in that dream? Well, I did find significant correlations between his life/physiology and my life/physiology so this may be a retro-vision. However, although it cannot be ruled out that this indeed happened, there are no public reports of anything similar happening. And to make it clear again - I do not claim I was N. Tesla in a past life, I only claim correlation. And even with that correlation, it is still possible that this dream is not much correlated with real past reality.

7.5 The Simpsons

I have dreamed a Simpsons cartoon on 2022.05.05. Dreaming cartoons is unusual for me (in fact, I don't remember dreaming one before) and since it has been a couple of years since the last time I even watched a cartoon I suspect there's some deeper meaning here.

There was nothing special in the dream itself - Homer was launching himself into the air and flying towards some big animal or big sculpture of an animal, possibly an elephant or something dragon like, all inside a dome building.

While the content could have a meaningful interpretation I don't think the content itself is important here. But this would be interesting if this is the content of an Simpsons episode I'm effectively destined to watch sometime in the future.

So I've checked what is the current season of Simpsons - it was season 33. Now, 33 is one of the special numbers for me (I frequently encounter it in synchronicity events), so one could interpret the signal as a possible confirmation that I'm on the right track (and that's what originally popped up in my mind), but - as my experience with synchronicity suggests - the ambiguity is too large and that particular interpretation may simply be the most desired interpretation. On the other hand, the first thing that comes into mind without much thinking can often be correct as it stems from subconscious, and subconscious is highly correlated with synchronicity. But again, only time will tell for sure.

The number I most frequently encounter in synchronicity events is 22-23. Interestingly, Simpsons cartoons are typically 22-23 minutes in length and there are usually 22-23 episodes in a season.

I did watch Simpsons occasionally in the past and there is a possibility that this is a [*forgotten*] scene from an episode I watched years ago - although my dreams are generally not retro-visions of my current life, rather influenced by it, it is probably possible for older *forgotten* memories to reappear as retro-visions in some form.

Thus, if I now start watching older seasons and I encounter such an episode, this would still be interesting - it would either prove that retro-visions of *forgotten* memories occur in dreams (implying that I've watched the episode sometime in the past) or prove that I have, effectively, dreamed this particular future event (regardless of whether it is a rewatch or not). However, it would be difficult to tell what exactly it is - the former or the latter.

But if this scene occurs in an episode I surely haven't watched before, it would have to be a vision of future. Therefore, I have started watching new seasons of Simpsons (before I try earlier ones) to test the hypothesis.

I'm sure I haven't watched any episode from season 30 onwards so I'm trying these first. So far, I haven't seen anything similar to the dreamed scene.

7.6 Death of anonymous

I was in a car on a parking lot, daylight, feeling anxious. Someone in another car to the right was being shot at. At one point I see the wind-shield broken on that car and a man (40-60 y) lying on the ground behind the car. On the left, there was a big truck. I had a strong feeling this was next to a sea, although I did not see it (possibly a city harbour).

I was thinking whether I should get out of the car, but I was afraid I could get shot too. I think I did get out at one point. I saw some people in the distance, someone possibly pointing in this direction. Dream ended (I didn't think I was shot at the time however).

Although this dream doesn't seem so special, it feels *out of context* for me (I did not feel like I was myself in it) and it was traumatic. This qualifies it as potentially non-local so I decided to write it down. I find this unlikely to be correlated with my own past or future incarnations though. It might be simply a vision of the event happening at the time (2022.08.29, 01-07 AM CET) somewhere in the world - assuming that's possible, in which case I'm not sure why I received it (future might clarify if there is a deeper meaning) but my soul should be entangled with this one in some way.

7.7 Hallucinating zombies

I had a very strange day recently (\approx 2022.10.23). I had a hangover that day and didn't get much sleep the night before. I don't generally hallucinate while fully awake (whether I have a hangover or not), but that day I was seeing a lot of strange transparent figures throughout the day. I was aware these figures were not there in reality, after all, they were just dark silhouettes, but I could clearly resemble that these figures represent humans or humanoids.

The figures were present regardless of whether my eyes were open or closed so clearly the phenomena was not part of external reality. Apparently, I was dreaming while awake, although the brain was dominantly rendering external reality (rendering of a dream was limited to numb silhouettes).

This is not the first time I'm experiencing *augmented* reality, it just never lasted so long before and hallucinations were generally not visual, rather auditory - lately, I have been occasionally experiencing very realistic sounds (like human voices) for a brief time after waking up - I concluded these were artificial only after I ruled out external sources. It appears, however, that such hallucinations are not unusual[15].

I have to state that I'm not ill and I don't have any mental disorders. This probably has some correlation with alcohol usage (alcoholics, for example, commonly lack REM sleep, which can lead to some aspects of REM sleep manifesting during wakefulness), but the question then is - why I haven't been experiencing this before, I'm not an alcoholic and

never was, but I was drinking more in the past and had much worse sleeping habits (mainly correlated with depression, which, however, I do not have anymore) and never hallucinated. Generally, my consumption of alcohol has been decreasing over the years and my sleep has improved significantly. Alcohol may be a trigger, but probably none of this would be happening hadn't my consciousness transformed some 5 years ago. In this mixture of internal and external reality I see a potential precursor to additional transformation, my brain may be evolving towards a brain similar to that of a whale.

In total, there were a lot of them, many were present even at the same time, but none was there longer than a couple of seconds.

However, during the time they were present their movements were strange - erratic. Closer ones were also often leaning towards me. Although I couldn't see details, I felt some had strange faces and I had a feeling these were some kind of zombies.

Here, zombies do not represent creatures that were dead previously and brought to life afterwards (like it is often depicted in movies). I believe zombies here are similar to the type of zombies that can be found in nature.

In example, the fungus *Ophiocordyceps unilateralis* is known to hijack brains of ants. Upon infection, the fungus leads the ant to an area suitable for fungal growth (e.g., forest floor) and makes the ant bite into a major vein on the underside of a leaf. It then produces mycelia about the ant's body which contacts the leaf and secures the host to the leaf. The ant eventually dies, while fruiting bodies emerge from its head to spread fungal spores[16]. This is how these fungi reproduce.

While this might seem cruel, this is an effective mechanism for regulation of ant population[17] and could even be interpreted as symbiosis on species level - too many ants in a system would probably lead to extinction of ants just like unregulated growth of human population leads to extinction of humans on Earth's surface.

Similar to regulation of ant population by fungi, fungi could soon be infecting humans in order to limit growth of human population. Therefore, what I was seeing here could be a vision of future.

Fungal infection should not be a surprising response of Earth's immune system. The question is whether it will come from the wild or will it come from human laboratories - as I'm sure anyone with *half* a brain knows what unlimited growth leads to.

Interestingly, over the last couple of years, I was often wondering why I am encountering so many zombie movies (I didn't watch many of them though, they're more or less the same) and now I was *in* a zombie movie myself.

This may be a relatively meaningless coincidence, however, deep research and extensive experience of synchronicity have moulded me into a man who cannot dismiss coincidences so easily.

So here's one possible interpretation of what the subconscious is suggesting to me.

During accelerated evolution, viruses (and - in the current event - humans as well, directly or indirectly) are likely to be involved in adaptation of fungi to higher temperatures and, therefore, possible zombification of humans. The signals announcing this[18] may already be here[19]. It may be an additional vector in predicted regulation of human population size[20].

7.8 Odd sentences

Sometimes I wake up with an odd sentence in my head. A couple of days ago I woke up with this one: "The extended array of family clocks all around the world." (this is not a translation, the sentence was in US English). It's very weird, where did that come from? "Family clock" - is that a thing? As I woke up I did not remember any kind of dream, just the sentence. Was it taken out of some context or is it just some pseudo-random thing constructed by the brain?

2026.02.03

This reminds me of AI chatbots and their *hallucinations*. So it makes one wonder.. How would brain behave without the coupled soul? Probably very similarly to LLM's. Without the quantum or quantum-like reasoning provided by the soul, the brain becomes a deterministic machine. Thus, the sentence above may be something the brain constructed as the soul decoupled from the brain to some degree. After all, even during normal operation, the soul is probably not constantly coupled to the brain, rather the coupling/decoupling occurs at certain frequencies (in fact, coupling may be the effect of associated wave-function collapse) - probably brainwave frequencies.

This is interesting because humans have recently started growing brain-like organoids in laboratories. If there is no soul coupling with such tissue, it should remain unconscious and fully deterministic on the scale of the system (note that the neural cells themselves probably are coupled

to souls even if the network is not).

If such system remains unconscious even with significant growth and complexity, it would imply there is no soul coupled to it and it would represent another evidence in favour of the existence of souls.

The more autonomous is the development process, however, the more likely is that the soul is coupling to it. In other words, a brain grown similarly to its normal growth in embryos is more likely to be soul-coupled, but a neural network composed from smaller parts assembled and stitched together, unlikely. This is, after all, the reason why computers and algorithms don't have souls - they are not evolved or developed self-organized distinct entities, they both represent assembly of parts externally organized and stitched together.

7.9 Multiple VR experiences (2024.01.29)

Multiple high-res CGI dreams today in multiple sleep cycles. In the first, I was sliding to the left (or, perhaps more appropriately, the content was sliding to the right), I saw a little girl drawing/painting something on a big canvas. Right next to her was a pile of painted canvases on which the top painting (at least) was morphing from one image to the next, time was apparently accelerated. Next I saw a glass door/window and some nature outside, including a lake. This too was changing quickly through the seasons. But then the context was changed, suddenly I was in a different environment. In front of me there was a uni-coloured glassy (semi-transparent) character (avatar), it looked humanoid but the face didn't look so human. It seemed as it was bugging me in some way. At one point I jumped up, looking him from above while he was saying something to me, then, on the left side, I noticed a figure, I believe in a police uniform, running towards me with a flash-light as it was apparently dark on that side. This then seems like the context was a superposition of two different VR games.

I had at least two more similar dreams in two different sleep cycles. In one of them I was a character in a first person shooter (FPS) game (similar to Call of Duty), but there were only two players, the other character I sensed to be a friend who I've seen recently. And that's not all, there's some synchronicity here. About 6-8 hours before I had these dreams, I was setting up a VR headset, some 8 km away.

But I never played an VR game in my life! I never was really interested much in VR, I don't like wearing computers and I usually have my hair in a ponytail, so, for the most of the time of the mentioned setup I didn't even wear the VR headset properly. I did 3-4 VR headset setups in my life, all within the last 12 months or so, but I always only wore the headset as much as required by the setup procedure (no game-playing or game characters involved, only the boring setup interface). As noted before, I very rarely play games, and when I do these

are usually 2D games, the same or similar to games I played 20 years ago (point 'n' click adventures, real-time strategies). With no experience with VR games and little experience with 3D games in general, why are my dreams suddenly being immersed in VR games? And why now? Why didn't I dream games when I was a kid, when I did play games more often? Nothing has changed in my life recently and certainly nothing that I could interpret as something that could stimulate this kind of dreams (yes, the correlation with VR setups exists, but, as noted, I did not dream VR setups, rather full VR experiences). How likely is for the brain even to create high-res VR experiences if one hasn't experienced them before in real life? Is it a coincidence that I started having this kind of dreams at the time of maturation and increasing consumption of VR content by humans as species?

Note that the first CGI dream I had was a couple of years ago - considerable time before I did the VR headset setups.

The only logical and plausible explanation involves either precognition or transfer of information through channels of entanglement (correlation). My first CGI dream suggests precognition may be involved, others suggest information transfer between highly correlated events.

Note however that one does not preclude the other.

In CR, I have postulated that all forces are based on [changes] in entanglement (correlation). Strength of entanglement and distance in entanglement is generally manifested as distance in certain dimension of space (including time). High entanglement is then correlated with interactions such as high attraction and high repulsion, generally - with higher information exchange. When I was wearing the VR headset, I was doing the same thing a lot of other people may have been doing. All these events were highly correlated in time (distance in time was a lowly relative 0). I believe, therefore, that my recent dreams were based on games other people were playing. Every time we experience something new as a species, the [superposition of the] information about the event is transferred to correlated individuals, even those who never had such experience before. The quality and amount of information transfer will depend on the strength of entanglement and the ability of proper interpretation in the individual.

Note that in one dream I sensed that one of the characters in the game was a friend. This does not imply local production of information, the feeling (or any other element in a dream) can simply be a local inter-

pretation (one cannot transfer feelings but can transfer information to stimulate them). In other words, if this dream was based on remote VR experience, the character may have been a friend of the person playing the actual game, this was then replicated in my dream and made me feel the same.

In CR, everything is relative. Where do we or our consciousness end? It's relative. Our top layer of consciousness may be strongly localized, and one can claim our bodies are strongly localized (if one neglects, for example, its electro-magnetic and gravitational imprint), but what about deeper layers of subconsciousness?

Based on all evidence, any self-organization of correlated *micro*-conscious individuals can be interpreted as an organ[ism] of its own, more or less localized and more or less conscious. In some cases, particularly in longer-lasting organizations and correlations, it probably represents a precursor of an organ[ism]. The ordinary brain is simply one manifestation of localized entanglements, coupled and correlated with more or less localized consciousness. One can then correlate the entire human species with a certain hallucination. With the evidence above, obviously the individuals can affect this hallucination but the hallucination can also affect individuals subconsciously. Given the ubiquitous relativity, it would be generally inappropriate to claim that one thing emerges from the other. Causality can be weak or strong and can be inverted. In some cases, the hallucination will be effectively guiding individuals to particular structure and function (or, particular eigenstate), in other cases, *vice versa*. Positive and negative feedbacks are possible. In embryonic development, positive feedback may be interpreted as normal development, negative feedback as influence of a disease. Instinct, obviously, has two components - the component based on innate or local memory and the other component based on future and/or remote events, or non-local experiences of correlated entities.

Although I have developed my theories and hypotheses independently, somewhat similar hypotheses, as I became aware eventually, already exist. One is the hypothesis of morphic fields and morphic resonance by R. Sheldrake[21], and the above can be interpreted as evidence for that hypothesis as well. There's additional evidence in his works, so I recommend checking these out. The existence of fields in biology has been, however, proposed by others even before Sheldrake. Notable example is A. Gurwitsch's field theory of organismal development.

7.10 World Wars (2024.01.31)

I was in a hangar of an airfield (military, I believe) with some other guy. I was standing near the entrance, looked up, and the squadron of warplanes flew to the right. I had a feeling this was either west or east from my standpoint, rather than north or south. At that point I felt unease. A large flag appeared in the air above, I felt this was a Russian flag but something was very odd about it, it didn't look like Russian flag. I don't remember the colours but I remember there were stars on it, which I interpret as a reference to US, EU, China, Kosovo and/or Bosnia and Herzegovina. Then it disappeared and another flag appeared, this one had a white strip on the bottom and an emblem on the upper left. I thought Slovakia/Slovenia but then the flag would have to be upside down. It is interesting that Russian flag is the same as the flags of Slovakia and Slovenia, only the emblem is different between them. So this could be the upside down Russian flag as well, otherwise it would have to be the flag of Serbia.

So obviously, multiple interpretations are possible, but multiple correct interpretations are common in nature..

If the flag is indeed upside down, and maybe both flags were upside down, this could be telling me something about my geographical location. In that case, I was located north (facing south) and the planes were moving to the east. Further below I will assume this is the correct interpretation, but I could be wrong (although, I'm probably not, as my consciousness and subconsciousness know each other pretty well by now).

Note that, in case of the World War III, these 3 countries (Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia) will potentially align with Russia. For Serbia this is almost certain, for Slovakia this is increasingly becoming certain[22]. For Slovenia this seems unlikely at this point, but in these times, things can change quickly. Perhaps Slovenia won't align with Russia but will abandon its alignment with the other side as well, becoming neutral.

I got out of the hangar and looked to the left (west, according to the above interpretation). Another squadron was approaching and I felt we're gonna get bombed. Soon after, bombs started falling and I was trying to escape. I moved down-left (north-west) some distance away and the dream ended.

This dream could represent multiple similar events happening at different times:

1. NATO bombing Serbia in 1999, during the Kosovo war,
2. Someone bombing Serbia sometime in the future (Kosovo/Serbia tensions are present again),
3. a false flag operation with an aim to provoke a NATO-Russia conflict (in Slovakia?), starting a World War III (warplanes here may be drones),

4. a conflict between Serbia and Bosnia and Herzegovina and/or Kosovo.

2025.01.25

Things are changing quickly indeed. After a year, Slovakia's leadership is still pro-Russian, but it seems it could become another Ukraine soon[23]. Initially unlikely, the probability for a false flag operation in Slovakia has now just increased significantly. If my subconscious hint above is right, a regime change in Slovakia may be *right about the corner*.

2025.11.05

Everything seems possible now. Even Serbia is increasingly aligning with EU/NATO[24]. Serbia's "betrayal" now gives meaning to the interpretation of the Serbian flag as an upside-down Russian flag... And the stars I saw on the flag could indicate Serbia/EU alignment. A war in Serbia makes sense from another perspective - a karmic one. Serbia has been waging wars outside its borders *recently* (e.g., in Croatia, Bosnia). Now, karma can work in different ways, but who knows. I do believe the US will at some point experience war because it waged a lot of wars outside its borders, the same could happen in Serbia. Tensions are high. This time it could be Russia bombing Serbia's government due to its misalignment with the Serbian population, which is not so inclined towards EU/NATO, rather more towards Moscow.

Interestingly, recently, news started emerging with various officials in the West saying NATO countries should start preparing for the war against Russia[25]. Previously, the West predicted the Russian invasion of Ukraine (after it provoked it). It would not be surprising that someone is planning something bigger that would indeed result in a NATO-Russia conflict in the future.

Naturally, this dream was constructed by my subconsciousness, possibly influenced by recent news, but perhaps it is also something more - [a reconstruction of] a real event, happening in the past and/or the future. Lately my dreams do tend to be a superposition of multiple interpretations. The number of interpretations probably depends on the number/strength of entanglements between the individual and the environment in space/time. The superposition is probably also correlated with the ability to see or sense/reconstruct events farther into the past and future.

7.11 Clouds of Neptune (2024.12.27)

Perhaps not extraordinary, but an interesting dream nonetheless. I found myself in what may be a garden, daylight. There was a special tree there. Some story

about people discovering some peculiar clouds on Neptune was running through my head (perhaps I was reading about it, not sure). Near the tree there was something that looked like a telescope. The tree was leaned in one direction and had some hole (or perhaps indentation) where this telescope would fit. I wanted to see these clouds so I put the telescope on the tree, I looked through it but there was no magnification, the telescope didn't have any lens, only a glass on one end. There was some writing nearby mentioning something about planting tree seeds here. I thought how I'd like to do that. I saw a little hill then (I think the special tree was on it) and saw some oak seedlings on it. Then I climbed the tree. It had different installations on different levels (platforms). I remember quadratic solar panels on some branches. On the top level there were some roles of film (the discs holding the film where plastic and white) and some other stuff (perhaps a projector or a laptop, not sure).

I do not know how to interpret this dream, I cannot connect it to any of my experiences. It does seem like it could be a virtual environment.

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